

IPBES VA Chapter 4 - Literature review on values articulated in agrobiodiversity management / IPBES values assessment (4.8)

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Description

This review corresponds to the IPBES values assessment. The IPBES Scoping document for the values assessment highlights the need to assess (1) the types of values of nature that have (or have not) been incorporated into decision-making, (2) the types of valuation approaches incorporated into decision-making, (3) the challenges that have hindered the incorporation of diverse conceptualizations of values of nature in a range of decision and policy-making contexts and (4) the implications for different

stakeholders. Considering that biodiversity plays an important role in supporting agricultural systems and also that agrobiodiversity is internationally recognized as an essential element for building more sustainable, resilient and just food systems, it is common that within agrobiodiverse systems, multiple decisions are made, resulting in different outcomes for ecosystems and people. Thus, we conducted a literature review to compile and analyse information about the multiple values assigned to crops or their diversity within different agricultural contexts and social groups. We look at peer-reviewed articles where farmers' values associated with planned agrobiodiversity are explicitly expressed. Through a collection of local cases representing a wide range of agroecosystems at the global level, we aim to gain a global vision on farmers values of agrobiodiversity.

Process overview

Protocol

Considering that articles that study the values of different societies do not always use the term 'values', we defined a string of keywords for a broad understanding of values that would allow to (1) encompass values in a broad sense, (2) reflect farmers' points of view or knowledge and (3) indicate valuation processes considered as proxies of values. Therefore, keywords were formulated on active expressions such as "farmers' preferences". These keywords were tested separately and added to the list regarding their relevance. All the authors were invited to propose relevant articles from their own libraries. This list was used to cross-check the relevance of our list of keywords by making sure the relevant articles were caught by the keywords.

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** Systematic literature review of academic articles
- **Search languages:** English
- **Search engine:** Web of Science
- **Exact search date:** 10 March 2021
- **Sample extracted:** 3719 academic articles
- **Search terms:**

```
TS =  
(("farmer's prefer*" OR "farmer's decision*" OR "farmer's choice*" OR "farmer's  
justif*" OR "farmer's motivation*" OR "farmer's utilization*" OR "farmer's  
attach*" OR "farmer's judgement*" OR "farmer's assess*" OR "farmer's consider*"  
OR "farmer's valu*" OR "farmer's evalu*" OR "farmer's care*" OR "farmer's  
perception*" OR "farmer's perceiv*" OR "farmer's point of view" OR "farmer's  
action* " OR "farmer's manage*" OR "farmer's concern" OR "farmer's rationale"  
OR "farmer* prefer*" OR "farmer* decision*" OR "farmer* decid" OR "farmer*  
choice*" OR "farmer* choose*" OR "farmer* justif*" OR "farmer* motivation*"  
OR "farmer* utilization*" OR "farmer* attach*" OR "farmer* judgement*" OR  
"farmer* assess*" OR "farmer* consider*" OR "farmer* valu*" OR "farmer* evalu*"  
OR "farmer* care*" OR "farmer* perception*" OR "farmer* perceiv*" OR "farmer*  
point of view" OR "farmer* action* " OR "farmer* manage*" OR "farmer* concern"  
OR "farmer* rationale" OR "social importance")) AND TS =(agr*)
```

NOTE: The word farmer is used in two forms: a general form truncated by a star that can include the singular, plural or possessive plural forms (farmers') and a possessive singular form that was not supported by the first writing.

Treatment applied: a first filter was applied, where articles that were reviews or retracted articles, or that did not present empirical data, were dismissed.

Sample extracted: 3582 academic articles

Treatment applied: Of the 3582 articles, a subset of 1624 articles were screened to select relevant papers. For the screening, titles and abstracts were considered to select articles that focused their study on crops (at least partially), and that were based on first-hand data collected from farmers (through surveys, questionnaires, focus groups, etc.) to reflect farmers' points of view. From these initial readings, 335 articles were selected (according to their methods, country of study and level of agrobiodiversity). To complement this information and based on expert knowledge, authors decided to add 14 articles from their own library, to complement the information retrieved up until this point.

Sample extracted: 349 academic articles

Treatment applied: To classify values, we used a mixed deductive-inductive approach to separately build a classification based on the reading of two to five papers by six academics working on agrobiodiversity, confronting our results until consensus was found. We agreed on broad categories

and different levels or sub-categories of valuation. We then reviewed the whole list of valuations and aggregated some categories, which resulted in what we denominated as “the tree of valuation”.

The resulting tree was then tested and adjusted based on five other selected articles. Finally, 12 articles were selected **(A)** to code the values following the tree classification. They were chosen due to their representation of a diversity of case studies from different countries across the world, different agricultural systems (small-scale diversified agrosystems to large-scale industrialised agrosystems), different levels of agrobiodiversity and different species.

The factors involved in agricultural decision making were synthesised from the results or the elements of discussion provided by the articles from the value classification. These elements were completed by reading recent or emblematic reviews and case studies that synthesise these issues.

- **Sample extracted:** 12 academic articles to code values and prepare the tree classification
- **Fields extracted (A):**
 - Abrev
 - Publication year
 - Author
 - Title
 - Publication title
 - DOI
 - URL
 - Abstract note
 - Country
 - Level
- **Location and format of the data (A):** IPBES_VA_4.8_07-2020_(A).csv

Further information on this review, as well as detailed results can be found in **(B)**.

Definition of files

ID	Name	File Type	Size	Description
A	IPBES_VA_4.8_07-2020_(A)	csv	22 KB	List of 12 chosen cases to code the values following the tree classification.
B	IPBES_VA_4.8_07-2020_(B)	pdf	589 KB	Results of the review